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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE MEDICINAL SAFFRON PLANT IN HUMAN LIFE

Abstract. *This article contains information about the history of the saffron plant, its importance in human life, its chemical composition, morphological characteristics, ecology and medicinal properties, as well as its treatment for various diseases.*

Keywords: *saffron plant, crocus sativus, carotene, riboflamin, calcium, thiamine.*

“.....It is a twister and a melter. It is also maturing due to the features of twisting and glues. Its heat is moderate, it opens blockages: it corrects the stench and strengthens the internal organs. Drinking saffron makes the color beautiful, the eyes clear, and the heart strong. It facilitates the passage of phlegm and strengthens the respiratory system”

Abu Ali Ibn Sina

It is known that the saffron plant, which is one of the medicinal and valuable plants, has been consumed by mankind for more than four thousand years. In the Neolithic period, people used this plant as a paint for painting on rocks in the mountains. In addition, they used it as a strong drop, and prepared attar goods and delicious oils. The first information about saffron was found in the remains of Sumer civilization. In the East, it was called "red gold". The reason of the saffron plant's value is that it is extremely difficult to grow, and despite this, it is unmatched in medicine and human life with its aroma, taste and medicinal properties. **Morphological features.** Saffron *Crocus sativus* L. is a perennial herbaceous bulbous plant belonging to the family of saffron. The diameter of the onion is 1-2 cm, 5-15 leaves, pale yellow, 2-4 mm wide, hairless. Flowers 1-4, yellow discharge, lower part purple, 2-4cm. Thorns are shorter than bulgur. The calyx is long, 6-7 mm wide. Its wild species are not found. This plant is grown in large areas in India, Pakistan, China, Southern Europe, Azerbaijan. The saffron

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plant blooms in February-July, bears fruit in April-August. It is used as medicine in medicine. [7]

Chemical composition: 10-12% water, 5-8% oil and wax, 5-7% mineral substances, 12-14. It consists of 13% protein and a small amount of essential oil, which gives a very sharp and aromatic smell. The solution of saffron flower buds contains such substances and vitamins as carotene, thiamin, riboflamin, flavonoids, calcium and phosphorus, which are necessary for the human body. The dried stigma of *Crocus sativus* flowers is used as a food spice due to its color and taste. Biologically, saffron belongs to a family with major active components such as crocin, safranal and crocetin.

Application in medicine. It has neuroprotective properties due to its chemically active components. Hakim Ayurveda emphasized that saffron improves digestion, strengthens the senses and respiratory organs, cleanses the liver, kidneys, lymph glands, suppresses tremors, improves blood circulation, brightens the complexion, and activates sexual power. In ancient times, women drank saffron water to relieve pain before giving birth. Antimutagenic and anticarcinogenic properties of saffron have also been determined. If you drink it with hot milk, it improves brain function and improves memory. Another most important medicine in human health is that when consumed with honey, it helps to crush and reduce kidney stones. Tincture prepared from it is used in the treatment of cataracts, one of the eye diseases. Nowadays, in pharmacology, it is added to the composition of eye drops. Its sharp and fragrant smell is inhaling has a positive effect on the organs and helps people suffering from insomnia to get rid of it. In addition, if you soak cotton or cloth in saffron water, it will relieve pain caused by working all day, stress, as well as tension caused by colds, headaches and ear colds. If we look at it from the other side, if saffron is used more than the norm, it will lead to negative consequences, for insetense strong tension of sensory organs, poisoning due to excessive consumption, several grams of freshly cut saffron

1-picture. *Crocus sativus* L.-General view of saffran

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cases of death are observed by eating. As an additional information, it is also worth saying that pregnant women should not take it without the advice of experts, because it can cause premature miscarriage.

Today, the saffron plant is used as a medicine in the treatment of more than a hundred diseases, and 85-87% of them have been cured. Saffron has many healing properties. For example, it is used in the treatment of oncological diseases. Even in the last stages of the disease, it prevents the growth of cancer cells. Another medicinal property is that it normalizes the activity of the stomach and intestines, nourishes all the cells of the body, so the feeling of hunger is less. If there is radiation in the body

Its level will low. Heals swellings and burns on the skin. So, it rejuvenates the whole organism. Considered the most expensive spice in the world, saffron is rare due to the tedious harvesting process and its extremely low yield. About 150,000 crocus flowers are needed to produce 1 kg of saffron. Saffron is the crown of the spice kingdom, highly sought after by gourmets for its unusual flavor and color. Harvesting requires patience and dexterity, and is done very carefully when the crocus blooms, which last only 2-3 weeks. Local women delicately pick these flowers, which last a day before courtship. Then begins the complex process of removing stains from the flowers and keeping the most fragrant part of the flower intact, using an extremely precise and ancient technique. Saffron extract is a spice with a powdery smell and a unique color. The spice is also rich in antioxidants, which can have many health benefits. Anecdotal evidence suggests that saffron can boost mood, boost libido, and fight oxidative stress. In general, saffron is safe for most people to eat, and it's easy to add to your diet. Saffron supplements suppress appetite and reduce cravings when used as a weight loss aid. Some proponents believe that saffron increases serotonin levels in the brain and, in turn, helps prevent compulsive overeating and associated weight gain. Saffron extract powder shows promise as a means of controlling compulsive eating, 2010 according to a small study published in Nutrition Research. For the study, healthy, underweight women took either a saffron-containing supplement or a placebo every day for eight days. week. The amount of calories was not limited. Today, the saffron plant is cultivated in various regions of Uzbekistan. For example, Samarkand region can be cited as an example.

Summary. In short, saffron is the king of spices. The great physician of the East, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, in his work "The Laws of Medicine" stated that saffron is used in the treatment of more than 100 diseases. Therefore, today, in order to ensure the health of the population and treat many diseases, this precious plant is used in all regions of our republic. Plant cultivation is being carried out.

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